

GLOBAL ISSUES IN INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS

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ABSTRACT

This study addresses a wide range of issues such as the global and regional impacts of climate change, migration policies, combating terrorism, environmental crises and the role of landscape architecture. Climate change is particularly associated with the combustion of fossil fuels and changes in land use, and it is emphasized that this process affects key elements such as water and food production. It is stated that poor and vulnerable countries are the most affected by these changes, while rich countries are also affected by the costs of extreme weather events. The study discusses the relationship between climate change and migration, especially in terms of its impacts on the livelihoods of poor rural communities. It is emphasized that climate change-induced migration is a controversial issue in international law and that existing refugee definitions need to be expanded. In the section on global issues, the role of landscape architects in the implementation of climate change policies and the importance of the expression of creativity, heritage, knowledge and diversity are discussed. Environmental crises and natural disasters are discussed by linking environment and security, and it is argued that these crises lead to various social and economic problems. The global dimensions of migration are examined in the context of the process of securitization of migration policies in Europe and the successes and challenges these policies have created. In the fight against terrorism, the importance of regional strategies and approaches based on geographical, socio-cultural and economic structures is emphasized.

Other global challenges, such as economic crises, health problems and pandemics, are discussed and the social and psychological impacts of these crises are emphasized. The study

concludes with an evaluation of migration due to climate change within the framework of international policies and recommendations on the future role of social movements.

1. INTRODUCTION

Climate change is now an undisputed global problem, affecting our essentials, especially water, food production and health. Modeling and projections show that even moderate levels of warming will lead to global and regional changes in climate. Poor and vulnerable countries, which contribute the least to climate change, are most affected. At the same time, the costs of extreme weather events such as floods, droughts and storms are increasing for rich countries. Anthropogenic (human-induced) climate change is mainly associated with the burning of fossil fuels and changes in land use. The paucity of empirical research on the relationship between climate change and migration is striking and more research is needed in this area. The consequences of climate change are expected to have major impacts on the livelihoods of people, especially in poor and vulnerable rural communities. Climate change migrants are a controversial issue in international law and it is widely debated whether the existing refugee definition should be expanded or another definition should be found for climate refugees. This study examines the effects of climate change on human mobility and emphasizes that climate change-related migration is one of the most important issues for both Turkey and the world today and in the future. The aim of the study is to fill the lack of literature in Turkey, to establish a general framework on the impact of climate change on migration movements and to serve as a source for future empirical research on this issue.¹

2. Global Challenges

2.1 Definition and Importance of Global Issues:

Global problems are those that have transnational impacts and often require international solutions. Climate change is one of the most prominent examples of these global problems. The burning of fossil fuels, deforestation and industrial processes cause an increase in greenhouse gases in the atmosphere. This strengthens the natural greenhouse effect and causes an increase in surface temperatures. From the end of the century to the present day, a temperature increase of about 0.5-0.7°C and a sea level rise of 10-25 cm have been observed. These changes are causing shifts in climate zones, increased extreme weather events, melting glaciers and sea level rise.²

2.2 The Role and Importance of Regional Organizations:

Landscape architects have a major role to play in implementing climate change policies. Our ability to increase the magnitude and intensity of man-made natural hazards offers landscape architects great opportunities for post-disaster reconstruction and for improving the resilience, adaptability and regeneration of the environment. Work in this area includes approaches to sustainability and resilience, creativity, expressing a sense of heritage and belonging, knowledge and diversity, and raising awareness of the meaning and value of

¹ 1-İlik, M. S. (2017). A new global problem, an old coping mechanism Anthropogenic climate change-induced migration and Turkey.

² Aksay, C. S., Ketenoglu, O., & Latif, K. U. R. T. (2005). Global Warming and Climate Change. Selcuk University Science Faculty Science Journal, 1(25), 29-42.

landscape architecture.³ In addition, landscape architects develop innovative practices to reduce the urban heat island effect and act by considering environmental costs. In the fight against climate change, landscape architecture is working towards goals such as designing landscapes that will become carbon neutral by 2030, designing open and green spaces, and keeping the global temperature gain below the critical threshold. These studies contribute to the concretization of carbon footprint in landscape designs and the development of mitigation strategies.⁴

The increase in greenhouse gas emissions from anthropogenic activities leads to global warming and climate change. Especially since the industrial revolution, the concentrations of greenhouse gases such as carbon dioxide (CO₂), methane (CH₄) and chlorofluorocarbons (CFCs) in the atmosphere have increased with the contributions of energy use, industrial activities, deforestation and agricultural activities. This increase has led to a significant rise in global temperature and negative impacts on many ecosystems. The impacts of climate change on biodiversity and ecosystems affect the productivity and habitats of species in aquatic and terrestrial ecosystems. For example, due to warming in aquatic ecosystems, species lose their productivity or migrate to cooler waters. In terrestrial ecosystems, plant and animal species, especially in tropical and middle belt forests, are severely damaged and their adaptation processes are negatively affected. Another aspect of global warming is the continuous increase in the concentration of CO₂ in the atmosphere. With the industrial revolution in the 1860s, this rate started to increase and today the CO₂ concentration in the atmosphere is approximately 350 ppm. This increase is a direct result of human activities, especially the use of fossil fuels and deforestation. International efforts, such as the Kyoto Protocol, are attempting to curb this increase, but there are still serious challenges and inequalities in implementation.⁵

3. Global Dimensions of Migration

Migration has become an important agenda item in today's Europe, both at the nation-state level and at the European Union (EU) level. International migration movements are recognized as one of the most important phenomena shaping the economic, social and political structure of 21st century Europe.

3.1 Regional Migration Policies and Practices:

Europe's migration policies have entered a process of securitization since the 1990s and migration is no longer an issue that requires only humanitarian intervention. In this process, Europe's post-World War II migration history has been analyzed under five main periods: withdrawal from colonial countries, labor migration, restricted migration and the post-Cold War period. Migrants, especially those arriving through "guest worker" programs, played a major role in the revival of the European economy until the 1970s.⁶

³ Yörüklü, N. (2021). Landscape architecture strategies for climate change and global warming climate change policies landscape declaration. *landscape*, 3(1), 43-55.

⁴ Yörüklü, N. (2021). Landscape architecture strategies for climate change and global warming climate change policies landscape declaration. *landscape*, 3(1), 43-55.

⁵ Demir, A. (2009). The impact of global climate change on biodiversity and ecosystem resources. *Ankara University Journal of Environmental Sciences*, 1(2), 37-54.

⁶ Özerim, G. (2014). The Supranationalization of Migration Policies in Europe and its Turn on a Security Issue: A New Era in European Migration History. *Journal of Aegean Strategic Studies*, 5(1), 11-48.

3.2 Successes and Challenges:

The successes and challenges of migration policies can be clearly seen in the process of transformation from "tolerant" to "control-oriented" policies. During this period, migration problems started to increase and this led to the development of national migration legislation to prevent illegal migration flows. From the 1980s onwards, the EU's immigration-receiving countries started initiatives to restrict migration from all sides, with new national regulations and increased border controls.⁷

4. Regional Approaches to Combating Terrorism

4.1 The Evolution of Global Terrorism:

The fact that the definition of terrorism differs in every society makes the fight against terrorism difficult. For example, a person who is considered a terrorist in one country may be called a "freedom fighter" in another. With the September 11, 2001 attacks, terrorism has gained an international and global dimension and organizations have evolved from ideological structures to structures with ethnic and religious motives.⁸

4.2 Regional Counterterrorism Strategies:

In Turkey, the importance of regional strategies in the fight against terrorism is emphasized. For example, strategies have been developed against right-wing ideology-based organizations such as Hezbollah and IBDA-C, and ethnic separatist organizations such as the PKK. After the 1980 military rule, changes have strengthened the foreign connections of leftist organizations and expanded their activities.⁹

4.3 Policy Effectiveness and Challenges:

Strategic approaches to the geographical structure, socio-cultural and economic structure of the region are important in the fight against terrorism. It has been stated that the mountainous structure of the region and the infertility of its soil provide shelter and exploitation opportunities for terrorist organizations, and that infrastructure and superstructure works should improve security and citizens' travel opportunities. In addition, the education system and psychological factors also play an important role in the fight against terrorism. These approaches emphasize that the fight against terrorism requires a multidisciplinary structure and should not be limited to specific regions but should be part of national security policies.¹⁰

5. Other Global Challenges and Regional Interventions

5.1 Economic Crises:

Economic crises observed in less developed countries are reported to have led to an increase in mortality rates of the general population. In particular, there is an increase in most major causes of death, with the exception of transportation-related deaths. Studies show that

⁷ Özerim, G. (2014). The Supranationalization of Migration Policies in Europe and its Turn on a Security Issue: A New Era in European Migration History. *Journal of Aegean Strategic Studies*, 5(1), 11-48.

⁸ KIRDÖK, C. (2020). The Phenomenon of Terrorism in Turkey and Strategic Approaches to its Struggle. *Journal of Academic History and Thought*, 7(2), 1117-1135.

⁹ KIRDÖK, C. (2020). The Phenomenon of Terrorism in Turkey and Strategic Approaches to its Struggle. *Journal of Academic History and Thought*, 7(2), 1117-1135.

¹⁰ KIRDÖK, C. (2020). The Phenomenon of Terrorism in Turkey and Strategic Approaches to its Struggle. *Journal of Academic History and Thought*, 7(2), 1117-1135.

the negative financial consequences of economic crises, especially on the functionality and efficiency of health services, need to be mitigated and the health system in particular needs to be supported in times of crisis.¹¹

5.2 Health Problems:

Pandemics are important health problems that negatively change social structures and affect individuals worldwide. According to Aydemir's study, these negative situations affect vulnerable groups such as children with special needs and their families more. During pandemic periods, these groups face more negativity than normal individuals and families due to reasons such as the closure of special education and rehabilitation centers, inability to demonstrate competence in distance education, and lack of educational equipment of families.¹²

Pandemics such as the coronavirus outbreak cause economic, political, social and psychological deprivation of societies worldwide and create negative effects on the development of countries. It is stated that such pandemic diseases affect human and social life in every aspect, and that this effect varies according to the conditions of the time of the outbreaks, the reactions of societies to environmental events and their education levels.¹³

In addition, the greatest psychological impact of epidemics on individuals is the shock and fear of not knowing the source of the diseases, their treatment methods and the age groups they affect. This situation emphasizes the importance of education, health, economic and psycho-social support services especially for children with special needs and their families.¹⁴

5.3 Environmental Crises and Natural Disasters:

The problems and conflicts that environmental crises have caused and may cause in the future have necessitated the establishment of a link between environment and security. Thus, the conflicts between environmental crises and the need for a livable environment have given rise to a security problem. Although environmental conditions are important for states in the classical understanding of security, if there is a choice between military and political interests and environmental protection, military and political interests gain priority. This has led to the centralization of environmental issues, which previously had limited, if any, space in global security debates. Sources of instability such as inter-state and local conflicts, poverty, unemployment, terrorism and forced migration have negative impacts on the environment. At a time when global environmental destruction is no longer just a prediction, but climate change and related migrations, war and violence are taking place. Erosion, floods and inundations, diminishing water resources, air, soil, environmental and water pollution are among the serious

¹¹ Falagas, M. E., Vouloumanou, E. K., Mavros, M. N., & Karageorgopoulos, D. E. (2009). Economic crises and mortality a review of the literature. *International journal of clinical practice*, 63(8), 1128-1135

¹² Aydemir, E. (2021). Problems experienced by parents of children with special needs in the context of the global pandemic (health, education, economy and social). *Istanbul Sabahattin Zaim University Journal of Social Sciences*, 9(18), 1-12.

¹³ Aydemir, E. (2021). Problems experienced by parents of children with special needs in the context of the global pandemic (health, education, economy and social). *Istanbul Sabahattin Zaim University Journal of Social Sciences*, 9(18), 1-12.

¹⁴ Aydemir, E. (2021). Problems experienced by parents of children with special needs in the context of the global pandemic (health, education, economy and social). *Istanbul Sabahattin Zaim University Journal of Social Sciences*, 9(18), 1-12.

and increasingly irreparable threats to the ecosystem. Climate refugeeism can therefore pose a threat to the natural environment. The aforementioned problems turn into a clear and increasing threat for people who are part of the ecosystem, as well as for international actors such as states, multinational companies and international organizations.¹⁵

6. Conclusion and Future Perspectives

6.1 Lessons Learned:

Regional problems and the lessons learned from socio-cultural structures that appear to have deliberately held the region back are emphasized. The analysis of the Turkish environment between 1961 and 1980, when the political polarization of the youth turned into armed conflicts and illegal organizations established their authority, shows that every wrong policy can cause irreversible damage. This emphasizes the need for states and law enforcement agencies to distinguish between "Innocent" and "Terrorist" and to be academically trained in counter-terrorism.¹⁶

6.2 Future Approaches and Recommendations:

Bilben's study evaluates climate change-induced migration in the light of international policies and discussions on migration policies through the concepts of adaptation and vulnerability. The analysis of the place of climate change-induced migrations in security discourses points to the shift in axis needed in the context of national and human security debates. The study concludes with general evaluations and policy recommendations, emphasizing the decisive role of social movements in the future.¹⁷

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